

Table 2. Effect of plant growth regulators (10 mg/liter) on germination of polyembryonic rice.^a

Treatment ^b	Shuang 13 (indica)				Shuang 3 (indica)				Lu 52 (japonica)			
	G(%)	R(%)	WS (mg)	WT(mg)	G(%)	R(%)	WS (mg)	WT(mg)	G(%)	R(%)	WS (mg)	WT(mg)
CK	98.1	6.3	44.75	39.62	94.8	29.4	28.60	27.82	72.2	5.6	50.21	52.00
IAA	98.7	9.5	47.73	44.67	94.1	31.2	30.42	28.81	85.3	6.0	50.33	54.09
KT	98.2	7.2	42.63	39.50	93.3	31.7	25.89	25.60	91.3	6.7	55.17	55.20
GA ₃	98.2	8.7	42.59	43.68	89.5	27.0	24.14	23.38	79.1	5.1	48.72	46.50
2,4-D	97.5	10.8	36.45	38.55	93.9	38.1	26.60	25.89	86.0	8.0	48.28	49.58
6-BAP	97.6	10.4	42.81	43.27	92.9	30.7	30.60	28.39	80.0	9.4	51.93	57.80

^aG =germination percentage, R = rate of twin seedlings, WS = weight of single seedling, WT = weight of twin seedlings, ^bCK = distilled H₂O instead of plant growth regulator.

increased rapidly. At low (0°C) and high (60°C) temperatures, the seeds did not germinate.

The effect of five plant growth regulators IAA, KT, GA₃, 2,4-D, and 6-BAP on rate of twin seedlings was studied with polyembryonic rices Shuang 3, Shuang 13, and Lu 52. At concentrations of

10 mg/liter, all growth regulators except GA, increased the production of twin seedlings. The twin seedling rate increased more with 2,4-D and 6-BAP (Table 2).

Seedling growth of indicas Shuang 3 and Shuang 13 was stimulated by IAA at 10 mg/liter; average weight of

seedlings also increased. KT at 10 mg/liter increased seedling weight of japonica

Lu 52. The optimum concentrations for increasing the rate of twin seedlings were 1 mg 2,4-D/liter and 10 mg 6-BAP/liter. ■

Inheritance of photoperiod-sensitive genic male-sterile gene in rice

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CIS28-10S is a new photoperiod-sensitive genic male-sterile indica rice. To find the number of the gene for its male sterility in CIS28-10S, I set up a field experiment Apr-Sep 1990 with eight F₂ hybrids and eight B₁F₁ backcross hybrids, with CIS28-10S as the female parent.

There were 50 single plants/cross in the F₁, 117-307 in the F₂, and 79-161 in the B₁F₁ backcross. CIS28-10S was regarded as the check. The proportion of male sterile and male fertile plants was calculated 25 Jul-30 Aug.

The F₂ hybrids separated at nearly 1:3 sterile:fertile plants (Table 1). Fertility separation in the B₁F₁ backcross hybrids also was obvious, at nearly 1:1 (Table 2).

The male sterility of CIS28-10S appears to be controlled by a single dominant gene. ■

Table 1. Fertility of lower generation hybrids, Xiangtan, China, 1990.

Cross	Grain fertility of F ₁ hybrids (%)	Separation of F ₂ hybrids		Sterile plants: fertile plants
		Sterile plants (no.)	Fertile plants (no.)	
CIS28-10S/02428	79.1	76	231	1.000:3.039
CIS28-10S/R5	85.7	29	88	1.000:3.034
CIS28-10S/PC312	81.1	61	185	1.000:3.033
CIS28-10S/Guizhouger	10.3	66	181	1.000:2.742
CIS28-10S/Suweon 290	7.5	59	180	1.000:3.051
CIS28-10S/Japanese glutinous rice	63.9	71	220	1.000:3.099
CIS28-10S/Zixie glutinous rice	80.7	63	179	1.000:2.841
CIS28-10S/Teqing	86.7	51	160	1.000:3.137

Table 2. Fertility of B₁F₁ hybrids, Xiangtan, China, 1990.

Cross	Separation of F ₂ hybrids		Sterile plants: fertile plants
	Sterile plants (no.)	Fertile plants (no.)	
CIS28-10S//CIS28-10S/02428	41	39	1.0000:0.9512
CIS28-10S//CIS28-10S/R5	53	55	1.0000:1.0377
CIS28-10S//CIS28-10S/PC312	64	61	1.0000:0.9531
CIS28-10S//CIS28-10S/Guizhouger	70	12	1.0000:1.0286
CIS28-10S//CIS28-10S/Suweon 290	80	81	1.0000:1.0125
CIS28-10S//CIS28-10S/Japanese glutinous rice	63	66	1.0000:1.0476
CIS28-10S//CIS28-10S/Zixie glutinous rice	39	40	1.0000:1.0256
CIS28-10S//CIS28-10S/Teqing	49	48	1.0000:0.9796

Space limitations prevent *IRRN* from publishing solely yield data and yield component data from routine germplasm screening trials. Publication is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., multiple or unique resistances and tolerances, broad adaptability), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.